

nitrogen atom (attached to amido nitrogen) in bond formation.

The new strong band in the complex appearing at 455 cm^{-1} was assignable to Ag-N stretching frequencies and further, two bands appearing at 320 and 290 cm^{-1} were attributed to Ag-S stretching frequencies. On the basis of these assignments, the following structure is given to Ag-BTSC complex.

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Stability Constants and Thermodynamic Functions of the Chelates of 2-Furylglyoxal-2'-Sulphonato Anil with Some Lanthanides

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Manuscript received 15 September 1980, accepted 30 March 1983

IN continuation of our earlier studies¹ on the determination of formation constants, the present communication deals with the determination of stability constants and thermodynamic functions of lanthanide chelates with 2-furylglyoxal-2'-sulphonato anil. The method of Calvin and Melchior² has been employed.

Experimental

The metal nitrates used were of high purity obtained from Indian Rare Earths Ltd. All the metal nitrate solutions were prepared in double distilled water. Metal ions were standardised complexometry by EDTA titrations³.

The ligand (I) was synthesised by dissolving 10.0 g of orthonic acid in 100 ml methanol and adding to this an equimolar quantity of 2-furylglyoxal. The mixture was refluxed for ~1 hr and allowed to cool when a solid separated out. The solid was removed by filtration and air dried. The product was recrystallised from absolute alcohol.

Fresh ligand solution (0.025 M) was prepared in purified methanol just before use.

The pH was measured on a Systronics pH meter standardised against potassium hydrogen phthalate and borax buffers. The glass electrode was kept immersed in purified methanol for several days before use as recommended by Zeidler⁴. All the titrations were carried out in a thermostatic bath maintained at 30 ± 0.5 and $40 \pm 0.5^\circ$. The following sets of solutions (total volume 20 ml) at $\mu=0.25$ KNO₃ (prepared in methanol) were titrated potentiometrically against standard carbonate free KOH solution (0.1 M) :

- (i) 10.00 ml (0.025 M) ligand + 5.00 ml (1.00 M) KNO₃ + 5.00 ml redistilled water.
- (ii) 10.00 ml (0.025 M) ligand + 5.00 ml (1.00 M) KNO₃ + 1.00 ml (0.025 M) metal nitrate + 4.00 ml redistilled water.

The medium of titration was 75% methanol-water (v/v). The concentrations were corrected for the changes in volume by the addition of alkali during titration.

Results and Discussion

The dissociation constant (*pk*) of the ligand was determined by measuring the pH of the solution resulting from progressive addition of a standard alkali to a ligand solution of known strength and from the formation curve obtained by plotting nH against pH values (nH = average number of hydrogen ions attached to a ligand ion). *pk* is obtained from the curve of pH when nH = 0.5. The nH may be expressed as

$$nH = \frac{[R^-] - [P] - [H^+] + [OH^-]}{[R^-]} \dots (1)$$

where [R⁻] = total concentration of the ligand.
[P] = the concentration of alkali added.

The *pk* of the ligand was found to be 8.20 and 8.00 at 30 and 40°, respectively.

An analysis of pH-titration curves of ligand with and without metal ions shows that the formation of chelate occurs through successive formation. The values of \bar{n} (average number of ligand bound per metal ion) were evaluated from the following relation :

$$\bar{n} = \frac{C_A - [A]}{C_M} \dots (2)$$

where C_M = total concentration of all metal species.
C_A = total concentration of ligand species (It is assumed for simplicity of treatment that concentration = activity).

[A] = concentration of free ligand.

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The values of \bar{n} obtained are of the order of 1 indicating the formation of 1 : 1 complexes of La(III), Ce(III), Pr(III), Nd(III) and Sm(III) below the pH at which precipitation occurred. The values of \bar{n} were plotted against the corresponding values of pA and the value of pA at $\bar{n}=0.5$ corresponds to apparent stability constants $\log k_1$. Bjerrum⁶ introduced the spreading factor (x) for the determination of the corrected values of \bar{n} . The refined values of \bar{n} were then plotted against pA . The final value of $\log k_1$ is equal to the values of pA at $n=0.5$. The values of stability constants are listed in Table 1. The data show an increase in the value of $\log k_1$ with increase in temperature. The order of stability constant at 30 and 40° has been found to be Sm(III) > Nd(III) > Pr(III) > Ce(III) > La(III).

TABLE 1—STABILITY CONSTANTS AND THERMODYNAMIC FUNCTIONS OF VARIOUS COMPLEXES

Metal ions	$\log k_1$		$-\Delta G$ (k cal/mole)		ΔH (k cal/mole)	ΔG (Cal/mole/degree) 30°
	30°	40°	30°	40°		
La ³⁺	4.50	4.55	6.279	6.558	2.184	27.94
Ce ³⁺	4.55	4.59	6.349	6.616	1.747	23.42
Pr ³⁺	4.62	4.68	6.446	6.745	2.620	29.92
Nd ³⁺	4.70	4.78	6.558	6.890	3.493	33.16
Sm ³⁺	4.85	4.90	6.767	7.063	2.184	29.54

The values of overall changes in free energy (ΔG), enthalpy (ΔH) and entropy (ΔS) have been determined by using the temperature coefficient and Gibbs-Helmholtz equation⁶. The values of these thermodynamic functions are summarised in Table 1. A perusal of the results shows that the value of free energies of formation becomes more negative with increase in temperature. It indicates that the complex formation process is spontaneous and the spontaneity increases with increase in temperature. It has also been noted that the value of stability constant increased with a rise in temperature. This indicates that the formation of all the complexes is an endothermic process. The complex formation is further favoured by the increase in the entropy of the system. It is indicated by the positive values of ΔS in all the cases.

The analysis of the results presented in Table 1 shows the low values of formation constants, free energy of formation and enthalpy changes for the systems under study. These values show that these metals have less tendency to form complexes with 2-furylglyoxal-2'-sulphonato anil.

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Kinetics of Ru(III) Catalysed Oxidation of Lactic Acid and Acrylic Acid by Alkaline Hexacyanoferrate(III)

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Manuscript received 10 June 1981, revised 12 April 1983, accepted 1 July 1983

DESPITE much work on the oxidative capacity of alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) involving Os(VIII) as catalyst, little work has been done on the mechanism and path ways^{1,2} involved in Ru(III) catalysed oxidation of substrates by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III). Oxidation of lactic acid (LA) and acrylic acid (AA) by alkaline hexacyanoferrate(III) was found to proceed only in the presence of catalyst Ru(III). In the present communication, we report the kinetics and mechanism of Ru(III) catalysed oxidation of LA and AA by alkaline solution of hexacyanoferrate(III).

Experimental

Materials and method: Stock solutions of potassium hexacyanoferrate(III) and sodium hydroxide were prepared from B.D.H., AnalaR reagents. The solution of ruthenium(III) chloride (Johnson Mathey) was prepared by dissolving the salt in hydrochloric acid of known strength. Lactic acid was Adamson (U.S.A.) and acrylic acid was E. Merck products. All other reagents were of A. R. grade except ferroin indicator (E. Merck).

The reaction was initiated by transferring the requisite quantity of substrate to the rest of the reaction mixture maintained at constant temperature. The kinetics were followed titrimetrically³ by examining aliquot portions of the reaction mixture for the consumed hexacyanoferrate(III).

Stoichiometry: The reaction mixture containing a known excess of hexacyanoferrate(III) over substrate was kept at 40° in presence $0.8 \times 10^{-1} M$ alkali and $3.52 \times 10^{-6} M$ Ru(III) in LA, and $5.0 \times 10^{-2} M$ alkali and $8.8 \times 10^{-6} M$ Ru(III) in AA oxidations. The amount of hexacyanoferrate(III) left revealed 1 : 2 stoichiometry between LA and hexacyanoferrate(III) and 1 : 8 stoichiometry between AA and hexacyanoferrate(III) as shown by eqns (1) and (2), respectively.

Presence of keto acid was detected by spot test⁴ as an end product in oxidation of LA while formic acid was identified by chromatography in oxidation of AA.

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